
Emerging Trends & Technologies in Library & Information Services

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Abstract:

Libraries are one of the foremost critical social institutions. No society is complete without a library storing information from the world over. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) have extensively impacted libraries and their services.

Earlier, libraries offered manual information resources and services to their users, but now, libraries are opening up to digitalization, primarily in the form of online libraries, e-Libraries, or digital libraries.

The employment of numerous modern technologies is possible in libraries. Emerging technology are technologies that has attained the highest level of acceptance. Technologies that support user services, instructions, library management, and technical services are included in emerging technology. These new technologies have given libraries all over the world fantastic potential to improve user access to library and information services. Libraries in developed countries have been using emerging technologies like Robotics, Cloud Computing, RFID, Big Data, Institutional Repositories, Virtual and Augmented Reality, Book Delivery Drones, and Web2.0 to provide library and information services. Libraries. This paper describes emerging technology, emerging technology in and for libraries through a survey of the literature that is currently available. There have been several benefits stated for integrating emerging technology in libraries, including an increase in patronage, cost and time savings, and brand loyalty. Also mentioned were the difficulties preventing the widespread application of developing technologies in libraries.

Keywords: *Emerging Technologies, Libraries, Issues, Impacts, Opportunities*

Current Trends in Library and Information Services:

1. Electronic Resource Management:

Electronic resources refer to e-journals, e-books, online databases, and other materials in digital formats, which are accessible electronically. e-Resource Management Software can be employed by libraries to trace the collection, access, authorization, maintenance, usage, evaluation, reservation, and selection of a library's electronic information resources.

2. RFID Implementation:

Radio-Frequency Identification (RFID) uses electromagnetic fields to select and track tags attached to library items automatically. The RFID-based library management system is the newest technology used to track inventory and strengthen library theft detection systems. This technology enhances the security of libraries and increases their efficiency by streamlining the processes and reducing human dependence. For the users, RFID

accelerates the borrowing and return procedures. Hence, RFID saves time and reduces library costs.

3. Cloud Computing:

Libraries across the world are adopting cloud computing to make library services more streamlined and cost-efficient. This library management system plays a significant role in building digital libraries or repositories. Cloud computing also ensures optimal use of library resources, infrastructure, human resources, etc. Moreover, the technology is also used for library automation and quick data search. Additionally, in a **digital library**, cloud computing ensures that third-party services can manage servers, carry out upgrades, and create data backups.

4. Internet of Things:

The best-integrated **library software** and **LMS software** have started using the Internet of Things (IoT) to transfer data without human intervention. Libraries use IoT to control inventory, prevent theft, and identify users. It also helps in improving the quality and speed of circulation desk activities. Moreover, IoT expedites reservation of books, fire detection in the library and its prevention, and streamline **eLibrary** services.

5. Big Data and Data Visualization:

Big Data and Data Visualization is the method of displaying a large volume of data through charts, graphs, maps, and other visual forms. This makes the info more natural for the human mind to grasp and makes it easier to spot trends, patterns, and outliers within large data sets. This technology is helping digital libraries become more globalized while accessing a vast amount of data. It makes the libraries

more easily accessible to readers who can find a plethora of information at their fingertips.

6. Artificial Intelligence:

Artificial intelligence (AI) uses the power of a robot or a computer that tries to do tasks that humans usually do. The most common application of AI in a library is the chat bots that receive directional questions from users and resolve them. They can alert the user about their book submission due date, direct a user to the relevant library segment, and automatically schedule appointments.

7. Mobile-Based Library Services:

The three main objectives of a library are to promote literacy, disseminate useful daily information to the people and encourage lifelong learning through its reading materials and resources. Mobile libraries bring resources outside of the library's fixed location to users who otherwise might not get an opportunity to profit from them.

With the help of mobile services like SMS and WhatsApp, libraries can produce new services and provide faster access to their collection. It also includes a learning management system (LMS), a software application that provides the framework that handles all aspects of the learning process and tracks your training content.

An example of the **best LMS software** is Moodle. The OPAC mobile application is a classic example of mobile-based library services. The platform is operated by SLIM Softwares and aims at converting conventional libraries to digital libraries.

8. Intelligent Library Search & Federated Search:

Federated search and Intelligent Library Search are techniques to retrieve information from many different content locations with only one query and one search interface with federated search. The technology complements main libraries in retrieving information quickly and makes indexing seamless. Libraries also use this technology for descriptive cataloging, subject indexing, database searching, and collection development.

9. Academic Integrity and Plagiarism:

Any discussion about **current trends in library systems** will be incomplete without mentioning academic integrity and plagiarism. Plagiarism is using another's ideas, words, theories, illustrations or graphics, opinions, or facts without giving credit. For students, copying others' work damages the intellectual integrity of their academic experience. Therefore, avoiding plagiarism has become the need of the hour.

Conclusion and Recommendation:

New technologies have established itself in libraries as a transformation in the deliveries of information services; there is rapid transition from hard to soft and print to digital as the case may be. The need for library users is also changing literally mimicking the changing global environmental climate just to buttress the point that this change is almost uncontrolled by evident factors like management system of libraries. The study carefully look into emerging technologies and emerging technologies for libraries, which include Robotic, Artificial Intelligence, Radio Frequency Identification(RFID), Internet of

Things (IoT), and many more, the used emerging technologies for service delivery in libraries, opportunities of using emerging technologies in libraries; to include, it has an impact on librarians' and the library's creativity, problem-solving skills, and self-image, it helps to process innovations and bring value to existing products and services, it strengthened library knowledge and opportunities for the future, and the challenges limiting the use of these technologies were as well discussed.

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